

ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF DISCOURSE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS THROUGH A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH

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Abstract. *The article examines the process of improving the discourse competence of future English language teachers through the analysis of the concept Motherland in pedagogical discourse. The authors emphasize the importance of developing future teachers' skills of effective communication and interaction in various linguistic contexts, which constitutes an integral part of pedagogical activity. The conceptual approach allows for the integration of theoretical and practical aspects of teaching, including the awareness of key concepts and their application in real educational situations. The study presents methods and strategies that promote the development of critical thinking, the ability to analyze and interpret communicative situations, and to build logical and well-argued communication. Special attention is paid to the integration of cultural and linguistic knowledge, which contributes to improving the quality of foreign language teaching and to the enhancement of professional competence of future specialists.*

Keywords: *discourse, discourse competence, text linguistics, institutional discourse, types of institutional discourse, learner-centered discourse, pedagogical discourse.*

1. Introduction

The effectiveness of communication largely depends on the level of formation of various components of communicative competence among future teachers: linguistic, speech, sociolinguistic (sociocultural), social, discourse, subject-related, and professional. A key role in this structure is played by the discourse component, which implies the ability to construct coherent and logical oral and written statements in a foreign language, taking into account a wide range of sociolinguistic and sociocultural factors [1, p.1139]. Consequently, the formation and improvement of discourse competence among future teachers should be regarded as a highly relevant issue in modern language pedagogy.

The urgency of this problem is confirmed by numerous studies conducted in recent years not only abroad but also within the CIS. For example, A.S. Dorofeeva's dissertation "Formation of Discourse Competence of Future Foreign Language Teachers" [2] is devoted to the theoretical and methodological substantiation and development of a model for discourse competence formation. Similarly, O.L. Kurgaeva's dissertation focuses on developing discourse competence among law students through project-based research activities [4]. The doctoral thesis by T.V. Ezhova "Designing Pedagogical Discourse in Higher Education" explores the process of forming general cultural competence of future teachers while studying foreign languages [5]. Furthermore, A.T. Nurmanov and Sh.B. Nishonova have investigated the introduction of modern approaches in teaching Russian as a foreign language in Uzbekistan [6].

2. The Concept of Discourse

The term *discourse* has become increasingly common in many branches of the humanities, including philosophy, linguistics, literary studies, semiotics, sociology, psychology, pedagogy, and language didactics. At the same time, its scope, meaning, and boundaries remain the subject of broad discussion.

Traditionally, discourse is considered in relation to the concepts of *text* and *speech*. The **Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary** defines discourse as “*a coherent text together with extralinguistic, pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological and other factors; text considered in its event dimension... Discourse is speech immersed in life*” [7, pp.136–137].

Teun A. van Dijk notes: “*Discourse is a flow of speech, language in constant motion, encompassing the diversity of its historical epoch, as well as the individual and social characteristics of both the communicator and the communicative situation. Discourse reflects mentality and culture—national and universal, as well as individual and private*” [8, p.47].

Thus, discourse is simultaneously understood as both process and product of speech activity, closely interconnected with social reality and various modes of human thinking. This multidimensionality explains the wide range of definitions and classifications of discourse types. For instance, scholars distinguish oral and written discourse, monologic and dialogic discourse, hypotactic and paratactic discourse, personal and institutional discourse, among others.

3. Typology of Discourse

For this study, we rely on V.I. Karasik’s typology, which is based on sociolinguistic parameters and distinguishes between **personal** and **institutional** discourse.

3.1 Personal Discourse

Personal discourse is learner-centered and is expressed in forms of communication where the speaker conveys individual thoughts, feelings, opinions, and beliefs. Its essential characteristic is its dependence on personal experience and subjective worldview. It is realized in informal conversations, diaries, personal essays, autobiographies, etc. According to V.I. Karasik, it can be divided into:

- **everyday discourse** (short, dialogic, colloquial interactions);
- **existential discourse** (expanded, meaning-saturated, monologic texts such as literary or philosophical works) [10, p.240].

3.2 Institutional Discourse

Institutional discourse, in contrast, is status-oriented and defined as communication regulated by the norms of a particular social institution [10, p.278]. It includes administrative, political, diplomatic, pedagogical, legal, military, religious, scientific, media, and other discourses. Unlike personal discourse, it minimizes subjectivity and follows established rules, although in some cases—such as the speech of charismatic politicians or public figures—individual expression plays a role.

In our study, we focus on the role of the concept *Motherland* in differentiating institutional discourses, particularly pedagogical, political, military, and media discourse. We argue that in these domains, the concept not only acquires distinctive features but also shapes the very specificity of the discourse itself.

4. Pedagogical Discourse and the Concept *Motherland*

Pedagogical discourse is defined as “*a systematic process that occurs in the course of communication between teacher and students, governed by strictly regulated rules and methods of the educational context*” [12, p.260]. Education functions as a social institution where teacher and students are positioned in hierarchical roles, and their interaction follows formalized norms.

Its main characteristics include:

1. logical organization of speech aimed at solving educational, developmental, and cognitive tasks;
2. coherence and cohesion of statements for effective communication;
3. argumentativeness directed toward educational goals;
4. completeness of utterances ensuring pragmatic efficiency;
5. predominance of formal style to maintain an appropriate educational atmosphere.

Within this framework, the concept *Motherland* plays a vital role, as pedagogical discourse directly serves the goals of upbringing. Specifically, it emphasizes:

- **Patriotic education** – fostering love and respect for one’s country, history, and cultural traditions.
- **Civic education** – instilling awareness of responsibility toward society, respect for law and order.
- **Historical and cultural heritage** – promoting cultural identity and historical memory as key educational values.
- **Moral and ethical norms** – nurturing values such as honesty, diligence, social justice, and responsibility toward others.

5. Developing Discourse Competence of Future Teachers

The improvement of discourse competence requires a multi-stage process that combines language skills, strategic communication, and intercultural awareness. Recommended methods include:

- **Text perception and analysis:** working with authentic texts (news, articles, interviews, literature) to identify discourse structures.
- **Case studies:** analyzing real communicative situations to select appropriate strategies.
- **Role-playing and simulations:** practicing interactions such as interviews, lessons, or conferences.
- **Contextual grammar and vocabulary training:** integrating grammar and lexicon into meaningful communicative practice.
- **Interactive methods:** project-based learning, problem-based learning, group discussions, debates.
- **Intercultural communication strategies:** situational analysis, cultural immersion, reflection on cultural misunderstandings.
- **Digital technologies:** online platforms, interactive simulators, mobile applications, podcasts, and virtual tours to practice discourse skills.

6. Conclusion

The improvement of discourse competence in future English language teachers is a multifaceted process requiring a conceptual approach that integrates theoretical foundations with practical strategies. Discourse competence goes beyond linguistic accuracy—it encompasses the ability to engage in meaningful communication across contexts, cultures, and situations. By combining pedagogical discourse analysis, intercultural education, interactive methods, and modern technologies, teacher education can significantly enhance both the professional and communicative competence of future specialists.

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